

WG Researcher Engagement: Introducing EOSC (SOA) at the 2nd Austrian Library Congress

Marie Czuray (EOSC SOA, TU Wien), Katharina Flicker (EOSC SOA, TU Wien), Bernd Saurugger (EOSC SOA, TU Wien)

The 2nd Austrian Library Congress took place from March 25-28, 2025, at the Austria Center Vienna, focusing on the theme 'Libraries: democratic - diverse - sustainable.' The event covered a wide range of topics, from AI and information literacy to accessibility, participation, sustainability, research data management and Open Science Cooperation. The EOSC SOA Working Group on Researcher Engagement participated in the latter, introducing the EOSC, EOSC SOA and its work. Curious to learn more? [Click here for the full article.](#)

Data Handling - Perspectives from Everyday Research in Austria

Marie Czuray & Bernd Saurugger introducing the EOSC (SOA) at the 2nd Austrian Library Congress, 28 March 2025. Photo Sonja Fröschl.

Marie Czuray and Bernd Saurugger, both members of the Working Group Researcher Engagement (WG REA) and the EOSC Support Office Secretariat, kicked off the presentation by highlighting the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) as a key development in European research data infrastructures. EOSC is designed as a federated system of research infrastructures that enables the sharing and reuse of data, services, and tools across disciplines and borders. Rather than starting from scratch, EOSC

builds upon existing infrastructures. Its goal is to support FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and collaborative research, offering clear benefits for researchers, including improved data access, enhanced standardization, and an expanding array of data, tools, and services.

Against this background, the WG REA supported the following goal: Aligning EOSC with the daily needs and requirements of research in Austria, while

Working Group REA

The Working Group on Researcher Engagement (WG REA) has been active since 2021. Its members represent a diverse range of institutions, including TU Wien, Graz University of Technology, University of Vienna, ÖAW, and University of Graz. Their expertise spans across libraries, research data management, data science, and social sciences:

<https://eosc-austria.at/working-groups/>

also fostering greater adoption of EOSC services within the Austrian research ecosystem. To that end the WG REA conducted a series of interviews with researchers across disciplines from Austrian public universities to better understand the needs and requirements regarding the sharing and reuse of data as well as issues with respect to trust in data quality.

The interviews were analysed, and preliminary findings were already incorporated into corresponding EOSC strategy documents via feedback forms whenever possible. In addition, the results will be presented in detail at the STS Conference Graz in May 2025 (<https://stsconf.tugraz.at/>).

In summary, however, key findings include (1) trust being closely linked to quality management and reputation, (2) a discrepancy between ideal and actual research practices regarding the reuse of data (testing before reuse is required but not necessarily implemented), (3) the need to improve peer review processes and quality assurance processes, (4) documentation being a relevant quality indicator (although the definition of documentation varies).

The EOSC Support Office Austria invites Austrian institutions to actively contribute to the ongoing developments in various areas, such as through Working Groups and consolidations. It is also possible to stay informed by visiting the EOSC SOA website (<https://eosc-austria.at/>), and subscribing to the EOSC SOA newsletter (<https://eosc-austria.at/newsletter/>).

Results and updates are shared on Zenodo as part of the EOSC Austria community. Additionally, the EOSC Café provides a platform for regular discussions and exchanges. For any questions, the EOSC SOA Secretariat is always available to assist you: contact@eosc-austria.at

Links

Website 2nd Austrian Library Congress:
<https://www.bibliothekskongress.at/>

Presentation:
<https://zenodo.org/records/15118048>

EOSC Austria / Zenodo:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/eosc-austria/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

Edited Interviews:
<https://zenodo.org/communities/wgreae-oscsa/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>